

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENHANCING CREATIVE AND CRITICAL THINKING IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14857720>

Аннотация

Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlashni takomillashtirishning ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. O'qituvchilar kreativ fikrlashni rivojlantirgan holda, o'quvchilarga yangicha yondoshuvlar, innovatsion g'oyalar bilan ta'lim berishi mumkin. Tanqidiy fikrlash esa o'qituvchilarni har bir pedagogik vaziyatni tahlil qilib, eng samarali qarorlar qabul qilishga yo'naltiradi. O'qituvchilarni bu qobiliyatlar bilan ta'minlash, ularning kasbiy malakalarini oshiradi va ta'lim jarayonini samarali olib borishga imkon beradi. Shuningdek, kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlash ta'lim jarayonining sifatini yaxshilaydi va o'quvchilarning bilim olish jarayoniga faolroq jalb qilishga yordam beradi. Mazkur qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish, o'qituvchilarning pedagogik yondoshuvlarini takomillashtirib, ularni innovatsion ta'lim metodlarini qo'llashga tayyorlaydi. Kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlash o'qituvchilarni murakkab pedagogik vaziyatlarda aniq va o'qimishli qarorlar qabul qilishga undaydi.

Tayanch tushunchalar: kreativ fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, pedagogik malaka, innovatsion ta'lim, ta'lim jarayoni, o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, pedagogik vaziyat.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается важность совершенствования креативного и критического мышления у будущих учителей начальных классов. Развитие креативного мышления позволяет педагогам внедрять инновационные идеи и подходы в образовательный процесс. Критическое мышление помогает учителям анализировать педагогические ситуации и принимать обоснованные решения. Обучение этим навыкам способствует повышению профессиональных качеств учителей и улучшению качества образовательного процесса. Креативное и критическое мышление улучшает взаимодействие с учениками, активизируя их участие в учебном процессе. Развитие этих способностей помогает учителям применять инновационные методы в обучении, что способствует росту образовательных результатов. Эти качества позволяют учителям

эффективно решать сложные педагогические задачи и обеспечивать высокие результаты.

Ключевые понятия: Креативное мышление, критическое мышление, педагогическая квалификация, инновационное образование, образовательный процесс, подготовка учителей, педагогическая ситуация

Annotation

This article explores the importance of enhancing creative and critical thinking in future primary school teachers. Developing creative thinking allows teachers to introduce innovative ideas and approaches into the educational process. Critical thinking helps teachers analyze pedagogical situations and make informed decisions. Teaching these skills contributes to improving the professional qualities of teachers and the quality of the educational process. Creative and critical thinking enhances teacher-student interaction, fostering active student engagement in learning. Developing these abilities helps teachers apply innovative methods in education, leading to improved educational outcomes. These qualities enable teachers to effectively solve complex pedagogical challenges and ensure high performance.

Key words: creative thinking, critical thinking, pedagogical qualification, innovative education, educational process, teacher preparation, pedagogical situation.

The pedagogical training of future teachers is directly related to the formation and development of their personal and professional qualities. The personal traits of a teacher include diligence, creative approach to work, independence, modesty, high cultural awareness, agility, quick-wittedness, composure, responsibility, meticulousness, determination, perseverance, diligence, conscientiousness, impartiality, well-rounded knowledge, observational skills, politeness, love for students, respect for their personalities, and others.

The teaching profession is a social-pedagogical phenomenon that encompasses both personal and professional qualities. Proper organization of this profession is crucial for guiding the educational process of future primary school teachers, as it addresses their needs, interests, motives, goals, and methods of implementation. This is vital for the development of pedagogical expertise. Like any other profession, pedagogical work requires special preparation (knowledge), experience, and expertise.

For a future teacher to effectively carry out their professional activities, the following personal qualities are essential: creativity, technical thinking, self-confidence, continuous improvement of professional skills, the ability to manage processes with emotional and decisive control, and the outcomes of professional competence.

Important professional qualities include responsibility, reliability, initiative, the ability to collaborate, and the ability to make independent decisions.

All professional and personal qualities have a dynamic nature and are continuously formed and developed. The sequence of their formation is always interdependent. The elements of each stage are interconnected and integrated. The stages of forming professional and personal qualities are linked through didactic integration, which addresses the connections between these stages at the levels of didactic integration and didactic synthesis.

Didactic integration performs a complex function. It envisions the integration of all components of the educational process (its goals, content, methods, forms, and educational tools). In other words, improving the pedagogical preparedness of future teachers through the didactic integration of the stages of forming their personal and professional qualities encompasses all elements of the process.

As emphasized, the process of developing the creative and critical thinking of future primary school teachers is based on the didactic integration of the stages of forming personal and professional essential qualities, as well as the gradual adaptive harmonization of organizational-functional capabilities with divergent and convergent thinking forms. This process is aimed at the development of future primary school teachers' personal and professional qualities.

Organizational refers to the process of organizing, structuring, and related to management; it involves the creation and structure.

Functional refers to the function, task-related, and duties.

When considering the organizational-functional capabilities of future primary school teachers' personal and professional qualities, it involves their ability to organize, structure, and manage the educational process, as well as tasks related to forming groups and working with them.

In the process of improving the organizational-functional capabilities of future teachers' personal and professional essential qualities through the gradual adaptive harmonization of divergent and convergent thinking forms, the

preparation of future primary school teachers was considered in terms of analyzing all available tools for solving a problem, selecting the most optimal one, and creating various solutions for the problem.

Convergent thinking is characterized by the analysis of all available tasks aimed at selecting a single correct solution. While convergent thinking is directed towards a simple solution to a problem that is already known, divergent thinking manifests itself when a problem is presented without a pre-defined solution method, where its resolution requires exploration. Convergent thinking serves to define a person's intellect, while divergent thinking defines creativity.

The following comparison is made to describe divergent thinking: "Divergent ideas can be metaphorically compared to an encyclopedia: it contains many articles, each on a separate topic. The articles are not directly connected to one another, but their collection constitutes a strong intellectual resource and potential."

The divergent thinking process has also been interpreted as follows: a problem exists, and as a result of drawing motivation from its content, intellectual exploration arises from various directions within the semantic space. Divergent thinking is lateral, peripheral thinking, revolving around the problem. The more distant the areas selected from the problem elements, the more creative the problem-solving process becomes. The essence of creativity lies not in the unique characteristics of intellectual operations, but in the ability to overcome stereotypes during the final stage of intellectual synthesis.

The main indicator of divergent thinking is intellectual activity that combines motivational and cognitive aspects.

Divergent thinking is manifested in the readiness to propose a set of multiple, equally correct ideas about an object, resulting from the acquisition and analysis of external information relative to the object. Convergent thinking allows for the integration of information into a cohesive structure that serves the primary goal of the research. In this process, creativity links an individual's high level of abilities to other qualities, such as imagination, fantasy, heightened emotionality, thinking, independence of thought, and the process of accepting experience and knowledge in the mind.

Conclusion. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the importance of enhancing creative and critical thinking in future primary school teachers. Creative thinking enables teachers to approach the educational process with new methodologies, while critical thinking teaches them to effectively analyze

pedagogical situations and make rational decisions. These two abilities contribute to the improvement of teachers' professional skills and serve to make the educational process more effective and innovative. The development of creative and critical thinking not only positively impacts teachers' personal and professional growth, but also has a beneficial effect on students' learning process.

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